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STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN NAMING ASIAN COUNTRIES:
A QUALITATIVE ACTION RESEARCH**

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The Use of Researcher-Made Geography Games in Enhancing Students' Performance in Naming Asian Countries: A Qualitative Action Research

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Abstract

One of the most challenging aspects of learning the Araling Panlipunan subject is becoming familiar with the locations of countries and naming them. This study seeks to enhance the performance of students in naming Asian countries through the implementation of researcher-made geography games that will serve as an intervention. The researchers of this study used the generic qualitative approach. The intervention followed a three steps process wherein an in-depth interview was given before the entire session to know how students describe their performance in naming Asian countries. After conducting the pre-intervention interview, the researchers have begun to conduct the intervention. There was a total of six sessions. Afterward, a post-intervention in-depth interview was given as the last step. The responses were collated and analyzed. The study shows participants' average knowledge and performance in naming Asian countries. This is constituted by four underlying factors, which are: unfamiliarity with Asian countries; unfamiliarity with location; difficulty in the pronunciation of country names; and difficulties in the spelling of unfamiliar country names. After the intervention, four major themes were generated: gained knowledge of countries' names; improved familiarity with the location of countries; established prior knowledge of geography; and eliciting interest in learning geography. It also shows four significant themes in students' insights on the use of the intervention: the need to improve geographical knowledge; reading and studying geography-related materials; incorporation of various approaches in learning geography; and fun learning. The study's results prove that using researcher-made geography games significantly influences students' performance through the gained knowledge and the pertained positive learning behavior, yet still makes learning enjoyable.

Keywords: *researcher-made geography games, Asian country naming, students*

Introduction

One of the most challenging aspects of learning the Araling Panlipunan subject is becoming familiar with the locations of countries and naming them. Students at junior high school, specifically in the eighth grade, are offered the opportunity to take part in lessons that present topics related to the geography of Asia as a region. It is essential for them to understand this concept to explain the idea of the continent in terms of geographic divisions, describes the physical environment of Asia, and come up with an overall geographic profile. Moreover, exploring a nation's physical, political, and social notions is significant for students because they will learn how a country is established, its recognized borders, and the cultural aspects of its people.

The disciplines of physical geography and human/cultural geography are both studied in geography. These characteristics are mostly displayed, conveyed, and illustrated through maps, diagrams, graphs, and figures (Amosun, 2016). Sozen (2019) added that geography, which is very important in understanding the place we live, should be an area of interest for students rather than just a course. Besides such as people give names, whether, for geographical or human beings, these are accompanied by associations of identity and personality. A geographical name often becomes a proper noun derived from a common noun written on a map (Shim, 2022). Therefore, for a description, a map depicts physical, human, and cultural aspects that can be seen on Earth, have been accurately measured, and are shown and drawn to scale on a sheet of paper. Maps can be used for various purposes (Amosun, 2016).

Globally, geography education is a crucial subject offered in various institutions, from preschool to post-graduate education. In Turkey, the first geography course curriculum, the GCC or Geography Course curricula, began to be implemented in 1924 in the history of the Republic (Sozen, 2019). Additionally, in Ghana, students' performances in geography at the West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) are understood via studies. This research was conducted to provide insight into policy and practice regarding how policymakers, instructors, teachers, students, and societies/parents could collaborate more effectively to enhance teaching and learning and student learning outcomes in Ghana's senior high schools (Anlimachie, 2019). Additionally, Adeyemi and Cishe's (2015) study introduces students to several methods besides the traditional method of teaching geography. In Indonesia, android-based Indonesian information culture education games are utilized. According to Kidi et al. (2017), games on mobile devices are a quickly expanding industry in the economy. As a result, the game is also utilized to foster a person's motivation to learn. Games like Geo Challenge, which uses the Android platform and has a game type employing a map, are examples of games like World Citizen Games comparable to geography and map quizzes. In addition, there are puzzle games like the Enjoy Learning World Map Puzzle, where the country name is labeled on a puzzle piece shaped like a piece of a country.

In the Philippines, in navigating the national geographic standards in the Social Studies curriculum, Gil, T., and Destura, R. (2022) explored the common teaching approaches in facilitating geographic education. Alongside history, geography instruction is expected to take center stage in the social studies curriculum. Geography-related expertise and knowledge have been applied in social studies

classrooms to interpret the past and predict the future. Accordingly, as to teaching approaches, Arato et al. (2019) endeavored to develop a 2D infinite runner–puzzle game called Juan Piece. This is done to determine how it affects students' understanding of Philippine geography and problem-solving ability. Android tablets and smartphones were used to engage in the game.

The researchers' observations show that Grade 8 students in one of New Bataan's schools need more familiarity with the names and locations of foreign nations. The researchers considered using the geography games they had created to improve students' ability to name Asian nations. This was considered because the researchers thought their increased motivation would affect the student's performance in country naming in their Araling Panlipunan topic.

This study is essential for students to learn the names of other Asian countries by their geographical locations in order for them to learn how to navigate and immerse themselves in cultures that are different from their own – where people originate from, what their customs are, as well as how to value the diversity of our human environment. Additionally, this may be helpful to students in order for them to comprehend the notion in order to characterize the physical environment of Asia, explain the idea of the continent in terms of geographic divisions, and develop an overall geographic profile of Asia. Thus, this urged the researchers to conduct a study incorporating researcher-made geography games to enhance students' performance in naming Asian countries.

Research Questions

This study aims to enhance the student's performance in naming Asian countries significantly relevant as one of the abilities necessary in Araling Panlipunan. This was addressed by using researcher-created geography games, which revealed the following:

1. How do students describe their performance in naming Asian countries?
2. How do the researcher-made geography games help students to enhance their performance in naming Asian countries?
3. What are the students' insights on using researcher-made geography games to enhance their performance in naming Asian countries that could be shared with others?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed Generic Qualitative Research, which means that researchers seek to collect qualitative data without totally relying on the principles of other recognized qualitative approaches, such as ethnography or phenomenological research. In this approach, the researchers give participants a voice to share their insights regarding their country-naming abilities since they took an active role in carrying out any actions that result from the research.

In addition, a generic qualitative design was used to look at people's reports of their subjective perceptions, attitudes, beliefs, or reflections on their experiences concerning things in the outer world (Percy et al., 2015). In the case of the researchers, they want to know how students describe their performance in naming Asian countries in Araling Panlipunan.

In this case, the researchers contextualized the approach using researcher-made geography games to enhance the students' country-naming abilities. This allows the researchers to explore students' performance in naming Asian countries and how researcher-made geography games could assist the students in generating their abilities to name or locate a country in Asia.

Participants

The participants in this study were 14 out of forty-five (45) Grade 8 students in one of the secondary schools in the Municipality of New Bataan. They are chosen as participants because they are brought together as one class where the researchers observe the problem under the study. Hence, other students in Grade 8 and other grade-level students were excluded from the intervention. Fugard and Potts (2015) recommend that qualitative studies require a sample size of at least 12 participants to achieve data saturation. Consequently, a sample size of 14 was deemed sufficient for the qualitative analysis of this study.

Participants were chosen using a method of convenience sampling. According to Taherdoost (2016), convenience sampling is the selection of typically readily available participants. Convenience sampling generally is the preferred sampling method among students because it is less expensive and simpler than other sampling methods (Ackoff, 1953). As to intervention, all 45 students were involved, but as to participation in the in-depth interviews, the researchers only chose 7 participants and another 7 participants for focus group discussion.

Procedure

Before the actual implementation of the intervention, the researchers thoroughly observe and submit to the institution's guidelines to ensure the standards, reliability, and ethics of the action research. The following procedures are established by researchers during the process:

Planning Stage. The planning took place after the observation class of researchers during their deployment in pre-service teaching, where students from Grade

8 demonstrated a low learning performance in the subject Araling Panlipunan specifically in naming a country. To address the issue, the researchers went through conceptualization regarding the appropriate intervention that can be utilized to improve their knowledge and abilities on the said subject.

Compliance for REC Approval. Researchers submitted the research study to the Research Ethics Committee for evaluation. The same committee ensured that the study's objectives, intervention, data collection procedure, and ethical considerations complied with their guidelines. This is also done to ensure the safety of all participants throughout the intervention's implementation.

Distribution of Informed Assent Form. The process of distribution of informed assent forms is highly required in the conduct of the study. This is done to inform the participants about the objectives and background of the action research and their role and rights in participating.

Action Stage. The following is the action phase that the researchers carried out:

Conduct of Pre-Intervention Assessment. This phase addressed the first research objective of the study, which was to determine how students describe their country-naming abilities in the Araling Panlipunan subject before the conduct of intervention. This also played an important role in determining the effectiveness of the intervention in the latter part of the study. The data-gathering tools utilized in this phase are in-depth interviews and focus group discussions using open-ended questions.

Administration of Intervention. The researchers administered the researcher-made geography games through PowerPoint presentations, mobile phones, and printed materials.

Conduct of Post-Intervention Assessment. The last part of the implementation of the intervention collected students' insights about their experiences and learning during the study, specifically on how the researcher-made geography games helped students enhance their country-naming abilities in Araling Panlipunan. This is coherent with the research objectives of the study. Similar to pre-assessment, the data-gathering tools utilized in this phase were an in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

Observation Stage. The data collected during the implementation process was thoroughly observed and evaluated to extract information pertinent to the research objective.

Data Analysis

As a result of their descriptive nature, qualitative methods permit the researcher to create a comprehensive, detailed picture in a natural setting. In qualitative research, one of the challenges is the open-ended nature of the data, as opposed to the exclusive use of numbers. It has been determined that the qualitative approach is more complicated than the quantitative approach due to the difficulty of reducing and identifying patterns in the text as data. Qualitative researchers often deem Thematic Analysis the most effective technique for analyzing descriptive data (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Castleberry & Nolen, 2018).

In addition, as cited by Xu and Zammit (2020), thematic analysis entails discovering repeated meanings across a data set, which is essential to interpreting phenomena (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). A theme is a particular pattern that captures crucial information about the data concerning the research questions, and displays patterned meanings throughout the data set. Rather than summaries of data domains, it pertains to a shared topic regarding the area of focus (Braun & Clarke, 2019). The terms "pattern" and "theme" are used interchangeably in the literature, and "theme" will be used consistently throughout this article.

Participants' responses to in-depth interviews and focus group discussions conducted before and after the intervention were thematically analyzed to identify themes from descriptive data gathered about students' perspectives before and after intervention implementation. Furthermore, the study recognizes Braun and Clarke's (2006) six theme analysis techniques, as cited in the study of Maguire and Delahunt (2017) in interpreting data:

Familiarization. All of the qualitative data that the researchers obtained during the pre-intervention and post-intervention interviews were subject to the researchers' review for them to become familiar with the insights and ideas that the participants provided.

Coding. During this stage, the researchers identified or highlighted texts of the entire data set that have commonalities in their meaning. These commonalities could be a phrase or a sentence. This information was converted into codes so that the meanings of the codes can be easily determined.

Generating Themes. The codes generated in the previous step were further elaborated to become the themes.

Reviewing Themes. The researchers reviewed the themes made from the previous steps by looking at them and comparing them to the qualitative data obtained from the implementation of the process.

Defining and Naming Themes. Definitions were provided for each of the themes that have been reviewed in order to explain and represent the responses that were gathered through interviews.

Writing Up. The final step is to write up the data analysis. Like other academic papers, writing a theme analysis requires an introduction to generating the research questions, objectives, and methodology. In this step, the researchers described how they collected data through open-ended questions and how they conducted the theme analysis.

Results and Discussion

The primary concern of this research study is to enhance the performance in naming Asian countries among selected Grade 8 students. In an attempt of addressing this concern, the researchers have conceptualized to use of researcher-made geography games to aid students and allow them to exercise this ability. The participants went through a series of processes including pre-intervention, intervention, and post- intervention to meticulously assess how the researcher-made geography games could enhance their performance in naming Asian countries. To be specific, the researchers focus on answering three research objectives which were presented in the prior chapter:

a) how do students describe their performance in naming Asian countries?; b) how do the researcher-made geography games help students to enhance their performance in naming Asian countries?; and c) what are the students’ insights on using researcher- made geography games to enhance their performance in naming Asian countries that could be shared with others?

As generic qualitative research, the responses were collated through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions and were analyzed through thematic analysis to come up with final themes that would generally describe students’ performance in naming Asian countries, as coherent with the objective of the study. In addition, as clarified in the previous chapter, the chosen students were identified based on the researchers’ observations before the intervention, making them the target participants of this intervention.

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Student No.	Code	Grade	Participation
1	IDI 1	8	In-depth Interview
2	IDI 2	8	In-depth Interview
3	IDI 3	8	In-depth Interview
4	IDI 4	8	In-depth Interview
5	IDI 5	8	In-depth Interview
6	IDI 6	8	In-depth Interview
7	IDI 7	8	In-depth Interview
8	FGD P1	8	Focus Group Discussion
9	FGD P2	8	Focus Group Discussion
10	FGD P3	8	Focus Group Discussion
11	FGD P4	8	Focus Group Discussion
12	FGD P5 FGD P6	8	Focus Group Discussion
13	FGD P7	8	Focus Group Discussion
14		8	Focus Group Discussion

Table 1 shows the profile of the participants. The data disclosed did not include sex, name, ranking, and location. As seen in the table above, the total number of participants in this study is 14 students. The researcher selected them via convenience sampling to gain further information for this study. Furthermore, as indicated in the table above, seven (7) participants were selected for the in-depth interview and seven (7) participants for the focus group discussion in the same grade level.

Students’ Performance in Naming Asian Countries Before the Utilization of Researcher-Made Geography Games

In identifying the students' performance in naming Asian countries before using researcher-made geography games, the researchers conducted an in-depth interview inquiring students on questions related to their perspective on their performance in naming Asian countries. It can be evoked that the participants were chosen at the convenience of the researchers because they are the students in the Araling Panlipunan class being handled as pre-service teachers. Through the pre-intervention phase, the researchers determined students' performance in naming Asian countries.

Figure 3. Conclusive Model of Students’ Performance in Naming Asian Countries Prior to the Intervention

The coding and theming result illustrated in Figure 3 were consistent with the research question to which the study aims to how students describe their performance in naming Asian countries. This, however, was the structure followed in the resulting process. Each theme has derived from the open-ended answer that progressed from coding to the theming procedure. In addition, the figure shows that students' performance in naming Asian countries is average. Together with this are the four underlying factors that constitute why their performance is average, which are deemed as challenges the students face.

Table 2. *Themes in Students' Performance in Naming Asian Countries Before the Intervention*

Themes	Core Ideas
Average Knowledge and Performance in Naming Asian Countries	Have an apt knowledge about Asian countries. Performance in naming Asian countries is average. Performance is average because we know some Asian countries but are not knowledgeable about all of them. Average performance because we are more knowledgeable about country names in Europe and the Americas than in Asia.
Unfamiliarity with Asian Countries	Unfamiliar with Asian countries. Unfamiliar with Asian countries due to some reasons: some of the countries are not well-known, inability to remember the names of the countries, and their relative lack of country-related knowledge.
Unfamiliarity with Location	Locational knowledge of Asia's geography is not particularly excellent. Unfamiliar with the location of Asian countries because some are close together, and there is a similarity in their names. Particularly in Central Asia, we have difficulty with the locational knowledge of the countries in this region.
Difficulty in the Pronunciation of Country Names	Have difficulty reading aloud the names of Asian countries and pronouncing certain of them is challenging. Particularly in Central Asia, we have difficulty with the pronunciation of the countries in this region.
Difficulties in the Spelling of Unfamiliar Country Names	The correct spelling of country names in Asia is also one of the significant difficulties that we have encountered in their performance. Particularly in Central Asia, the spelling of the countries in this region is challenging.

Before implementing the intervention, the in-depth interview generated several main themes and ideas, displayed in Table 2. The student's knowledge of Asian countries is average. Consequently, their performance in naming Asian countries is average, and four factors contribute to this average performance. These include unfamiliarity with Asian countries, unfamiliarity with location, difficulty in the pronunciation of country names, and difficulties in the spelling of unfamiliar country names.

Average Knowledge and Performance in Naming Asian Countries. This theme refers to how students describe their performance and it is mainly affected by having an apt knowledge about Asian countries. Five students expressed that their knowledge of this concept is average.

"Erm... ano Sir, dili pa kayu ko master sa naming gud Sir so tama tama lang gud Sir. Naa pud koy natun-an Sir." (IDI7)

(Sir, I do not master naming countries. So, it is just average Sir. Though I learned some Sir.)

"Kanang ano lang Sir tama-tama lang then naa naman koy knowledge pero dili pagyud as in bright gyud about ana Sir ba." (IDI3)

(It's on the average level, Sir, I have knowledge but I'm not really an expert about that Sir.)

"For us Sir like Grade 8 students Sir, we can say that our performance is just decent Sir to know some of the countries in Asia Sir. I think ano ko Sir just good enough to know at least lima ka countries in Asia Sir." (IDI 6)

"Erm... akong performance Sir kay 50/50 Sir kay nakoy mga nahibal- an nga Asian countries Sir nya naa pud koy wala nahibal-an." (FGD P1)

(My performance Sir is 50/50 Sir because I know some Asian countries Sir but there are also countries that I do not know.)

"Sa ingun nila Sir nga kaning 50/50 then akoa pud Sir, neutral ra pud akoa Sir kay dili ko kabalo tanan sa countries sa Asia Sir." (FGD P7) (As what they have said, Sir, it is also 50/50, then I am also neutral because I do not know everything about the countries in Asia, Sir.)

The responses demonstrates how students evaluate their performance in naming Asian nations, revealing average performance. Some have stated that they are merely average because they are familiar with some Asian countries but are unfamiliar with others.

Another two participants have narrated that their performance is average because they are more familiar with countries in Europe and the Americas rather than in Asia.

*“Same kay ***** Sir, 50/50 kay kasagaran man gud sa akong na memorize nga kuan Sir kay sa America man gyud Sir ug sa Europe. Wala kayu sa Asia.” (FGD P2)*

*(Same with ***** Sir, 50/50 because it’s mostly from what I’ve memorized that it’s really from America Sir and Europe. Not that much in Asia.)*

“Kanang same sa ilaha Sir, 50/50 Sir kay kanang kasagaran nga akong mga familiar na country Sir is sa Europe lang siya Sir ug America.” (FGD P6)

(The same with them Sir, 50/50 Sir because most of my familiar countries Sir are only in Europe Sir and America.)

According to studies, there is a developing interest in evaluating students' acquired knowledge. More frequently and in various disciplines, it is necessary to determine the level of students through various tests. In the instance of geography education in Spain, there is a decline and loss of knowledge for various reasons. The study by Garcia-Gonzales et al. (2023) was not only knowledge of the assessed administrative unit valued but also its location and representation, demonstrating the significance of location in geography. The results demonstrate that students' knowledge varies depending on their residence and the level of the country's structure they are inquired about.

Based on the responses of the participants, the performance of students in naming Asian countries is average. In addition to this, there are four underlying factors why their performance is average. The four factors are unfamiliarity with Asian countries, unfamiliarity with location, difficulty in the pronunciation of country names, and difficulty in the spelling of unfamiliar country names.

Unfamiliarity with Asian Countries. From the responses of the students, it has been shown that many are unfamiliar with Asian countries. A participant admitted with this have encountered this challenge.

“Dili kaayu ko kabisado na mga countries Sir kay even sa Asia Sir, ang Philippines na sa Asia Sir, dili jud tanan country akong nahibal-an Sir. Kana lang jung wala kayu ko nafamiliarize nga in-ana na countries Sir. Dili lang jud ko familiar sa mga countries Sir sa Asia.” (IDI 1)

(I don't know much about countries Sir because even in Asia, the Philippines is in Asia, I don't know all the countries, Sir. I'm just not familiar with Asian countries.)

In the same way, three other students expressed,

“...ang uban pud Sir nga wala pay nahibal-an Sir kay dili pamilyar ang countries sa Asia Sir maong dili kayo nindot ilang performance sa pag naming sa country sa Asia.” (FGD P7)

(...there are others, Sir, who do not know yet, Sir, because they are not familiar with the countries in Asia, Sir, so their performance in naming the country is not very good.)

“...di man jud ko as in familiar about anang mga country-country Sir. Dili nako familiar jud tanan sa Asian countries Sir ba, mao nang maglisud ko Sir like maglisud ko.” (IDI 3)

(...I am not familiar with those countries, Sir. I'm not familiar with all Asian countries, Sir, so I'm going to have a hard time, sir.)

“Maglisud gyud ko Sir kay dili ko familiar sa ilaha ba.” (IDI 4) (I have a hard time Sir because I am not familiar with them.)

There are other participants who narrated that they are unfamiliar with Asian countries due to some reasons. Three participants have expressed they are not familiar with Asian countries for the reason that some of these are not well-known.

“...dili pa katuod sa Asia plus dili pud ilado ang uban Sir.” (FGD P4)

(They cannot locate the countries in Asia plus the others are not well-known Sir.)

“Ang nahibal-an ra pud nako sa Asia, kaning country sa Asia Sir is katung famous Sir. Ang uban nga dili ilado kay wala pud ko kabalo kay wala man pud ko naga research about gud sa kaning mga country Sir.” (FGD P7)

(I only know about Asia if this country in Asia Sir is famous. The others are not well-known and I don't know them. After all, I haven't done any research about these countries, Sir.)

“...lisud pud siya ilhon Sir kay there are other countries nga dili pud kayu well-known.” (IDI 7)

(It is also difficult to recognize them, Sir because there are other countries where it is not well-known.)

Two additional participants are unfamiliar with Asian countries due to their inability to remember the names of the countries and their relative lack of country-related knowledge.

“Sa pagkuan Sir, pag hinumdom sa ilang mga pangalan Sir.” (FGD P3)

(Remembering their names Sir.)

My difficulty in naming Asian countries is that I don't have enough knowledge Sir about the countries. (IDI 1)

As it is defined, geography is about understanding the place where we are (Gersmehl, 2014). We can understand the place or the country that we live and we start by basically knowing its name. But it is widely understood that widespread place name ignorance exists among the younger generations of today (Hennerdal, 2016).

According to the findings of Hennerdal (2016), modern kids are better at identifying continents and oceans on a world map than they are at identifying countries and other places on a European map. The same notion is also true in Asia. These changes don't always indicate a general improvement or a deterioration in place location knowledge, but rather an adjustment to modern society, where schoolchildren travel to other regions of the world and receive news from them, and where precise geographic information is simple to obtain.

Unfamiliarity with Location. This is a challenge encountered by students in their performance in naming Asian countries. Participants' locational knowledge of Asia's geography is not particularly excellent. Three of the participants expressed,

“Sa location Sir, maglisud pud ko gamay.” (IDI 1) (In the location, Sir, I also have a little difficulty.)

“...nya naa pud koy wala nahibal-an kung aha sila dapita (FGD P1)

(Then I also don't know where they are located.)

“Mao gihapon sa ila Sir, dili pako katuod sa Asia.” (FGD P4) (It's the same with them, Sir, I don't know how to locate in Asia.)

Similarly, two participants reported having a difficult time, particularly in the location of a country having other countries or neighboring countries close to them.

“Erm... difficulties Sir kay katu ganing sa kanang, lisud kaayu I locate Sir ba kay dikit-dikit gani sila Sir.” (FGD P1)

(Erm...difficulties Sir because they are so difficult to locate Sir because the countries are very close to each other.)

“More on sa pag locate Sir kay wala man gud ko na familiar sa kung aha naka locate tung mga country nga uban Sir kay wala kay ko kabalo sa ila Sir. Like katung mga Afghanistan, Kazakhstan Sir then digkit kayu sila Sir.” (FGD P7)

(More on locating Sir because I'm not familiar with how other countries are located Sir because I don't know about them Sir. Like in Afghanistan, Kazakhstan Sir because they are close with each other Sir.)

Numerous researchers have defined geographic literacy as the knowledge of a location or the ability to locate a location on a map. Comparably, in the ineptness with the location of countries among students, in a study conducted in the United States in 1988, the National Council for Geographic Education [NCGE] attempted to ascertain the degree of geographic literacy among Americans. 14% of Americans could not locate the United States on a map, and 25% were unaware of the location of the Pacific Ocean, as cited by Utami et al., 2018.

In a different study, Oigara measured university students' low-middle-high- level geographic literacy skills. According to the research, students' geographical knowledge needed to be more robust. Torrens assessed secondary school students' geographic understanding of European countries and major cities. As a result of the research, it was determined that students lacked fundamental locational knowledge, as cited by Utami et al., 2018.

Difficulty in the Pronunciation of Country Names. This is a significant difficulty the participants faced prior to the intervention. Many have narrated that they often have difficulties reading aloud the names of foreign countries. Others have claimed that pronouncing certain of them is quite challenging. Three participants responded in the pre-interview by saying,

“Maglisud pud ko mag pronounce gani Sir, kanang unsaon siya pag- pronounce.” (IDI 3)

(It's hard for me to even pronounce Sir, on how to pronounce them.)

“Siguro mga pronunciation niya. Maglisud pa jud. Kay usahay mamali pa og pronounce sa ilaha.”(IDI 5)

(Maybe it's pronunciation. It will be difficult because sometimes it is pronounced wrong.)

“...dili kayu ko gastudy sa Asia Sir kay lisud siya ipronounce sa mga countries sa Asia Sir.” (FGD P6)

(...I do not study that much in Asia Sir because it is difficult to pronounce Asian countries.)

Other two participants additionally recognize certain countries and regions that they find challenging to articulate.

“...tapos lisud pud I pronounce, didtu ko nalisdan Sir sa mga Afghanistan, Kazakhstan.” (FGD P1)

(...then it's also difficult to pronounce, that's where I found it difficult Sir with Afghanistan, Kazakhstan.)

"Katung same Sir nga sa Central Asia siya, kanang lisud nga i pronounce." (FGD P6)

(The same Sir that in Central Asia, it is difficult to pronounce.)

Comparatively, a participant stated that she believed she already knew the correct pronunciation of a particular country, but this didn't seem to be true.

"Ang pronunciation gyud Sir. Maglisud gyud ko sa uban kay pagtoo nako 'g in-ana nya baliktad diay tu." (IDI 5)

(The pronunciation Sir. It is difficult for me because I thought my pronunciation is correct but it is the other way around.)

The views of the participants reveal that it is not sufficient to know only the names of countries, but also their pronunciation. Additionally, there is difficulty in communicating country names. The students' articulation concentrates solely on how native English speakers pronounce countries' names, not how native speakers of that country would pronounce them.

Difficulty in the Spelling of Unfamiliar Country Names. The correct spelling of country names in Asia is also one of the significant difficulties that students encountered in their performance. Three participants from the focus group discussion have expressed,

"Para sakoa Sir, naglisud ko...sa pagsulat sa spelling Sir." (FGD P5) (As for me Sir, I'm struggling...to write the spelling Sir.)

"Kanang lisud kaayu i spelling Sir ba." (FGD P4) (It's difficult to spell Sir.)

"Katung same Sir nga sa Central Asia siya, kanang lisud nga...spellingon." (FGD P6)

(The same that is from Central Asia that is difficult...to spell.)

Another participant expressed a similarity of difficulty faced by FGD P6.

"Lisud pud ilang spelling. Maglibog gali ko usahay Sir kay parehas raman gud sila naay mga stan Sir." (FGD P7)

(Their spelling is also difficult. I sometimes get confused Sir because they have the same stans, Sir.)

According to the United Nations (Department of Economic and Social Affairs), geographical names are essential because they provide a sense of place and a way to navigate, search for information, and organize the world in which people live. A place name is a reference point for their language and identity. Thus, the correct spelling of a country's name is essential.

Incorporating Researcher-Made Geography Games in Enhancing Students' Performance in Naming Asian Countries

The researchers proceeded to the study's second phase, which incorporated researcher-made geography games to enhance students' performance in naming Asian countries. In addition to imparting knowledge to students, the researchers emphasized addressing the challenges students face. The session lasted three weeks and consisted of a presentation and instructions about the games made by the researchers and the actual playing and completion of the games. The total duration of the conduct of intervention was conducted in six sessions.

After completing the implementation phase, the researchers re-collected data through in-depth interviews as a step toward achieving the second and third objectives of the study, which are to assess the performance of students in naming Asian countries after the use of researcher-made geography games and to determine the students' perspectives on the use of researcher-made geography games as an intervention to enhance their performance in naming Asian countries. The researchers can state from their analysis of student responses that there are changes and modifications. The responses and insights of the participants were used to generate a new set of themes.

Table 3. Themes in Students' Performance in Naming Asian Countries After the Intervention

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Gained Knowledge of Countries' Names	Have acquired knowledge of Asian country names. Acquired geographical knowledge. In particular, by learning new country names in Asia. Performance in naming Asian countries has improved.
Improved Familiarity with the Location of Countries.	Familiarity with the location of Asian countries was enhanced after the intervention. Progress regarding the locational knowledge they have learned. Experienced of identifying a country's location in Asia only by recognizing its shape and a general outline on a map.
Establishes Prior Knowledge of Geography	Gave prior knowledge about geography. Through the intervention, we have acquired prior knowledge to aid them in their future lessons, particularly in Araling Panlipunan. Able to use this newly acquired information as they mature.
Elicits Interest in Learning Geography	Inspired and motivated to learn more about geography, specifically naming countries. After playing the geography games, felt compelled to download a geography app to learn more.

Following the completion of the intervention, Table 3 displays the main themes that emerged. The researchers have identified four themes based on the responses of the participants: gained knowledge of countries' names, improved familiarity with the location of countries, establishes prior knowledge of geography, and elicits interest in learning geography.

Obtained Knowledge from Researcher-Made Geography Games

Gained Knowledge of Countries' Names. This can refer to the geographical knowledge acquired by the students. Additionally, this pertains to the students' acquired knowledge of Asian country names. Compared to their responses from the pre-intervention interview, a significant number of students improved their ability to assert their ideas. After completing and playing the researcher-created geography activities for weeks, most participants could retain the acquired knowledge. Four of the participants narrated,

“Sa amoa Sir, dako kayu syag tabang Sir. Naka gain mi og knowledge sa country nga wala pa namo nahibal-an Sir. Na improve siya Sir unlike before Sir. Sa una dili man gud ko familiar sa mga country Sir tapos katung nagpadula ka Sir kay naa koy na gain na knowledge.” (IDI 3)

(To us Sir, it is a great help, Sir. We gained knowledge of the country that we didn't know before, Sir. Our performance has improved Sir unlike before Sir. At first, I was not familiar with the countries Sir, then when you let us play the game, Sir, I gained more knowledge.)

“Kuan Sir maka...nakatabang siya nga ma mas makabalo, mas madungagan akong knowledge about sa mga Asian countries.” (IDI 4)

(It helped me to know more, to increase my knowledge about Asian countries.)

“Mas na improve akong knowledge about sa naming sa mga country. Mahibal an pud nila ang tama nga pag-pronounce ug kaning spelling Sir.” (FGD P7)

(I have improved my knowledge about countries. They will also know the correct pronunciation and spelling, Sir.)

“Maenhance ang akoang skills ug ang akong knowledge about sa geography Sir.” (FGD P6)

(It improved my skills and my knowledge about geography Sir.)

It can be observed that their performance in naming Asian countries became more confident as a result of their participation in the games and discussions. They gradually gain knowledge in naming Asian countries through sessions.

In addition, playing games helped students acquire geographical knowledge, particularly the names of countries. With the generated theme, it is also paralleled by other studies.

Similarly, reading blind maps requires knowing the name of the country being asked. In the study conducted by Ramlan (2020), it was demonstrated that using the World Map Quiz application improved students' ability to read blind maps.

In the study of Wilaiwan Wilairat (2022), the learning achievement of students was examined using the geography app Seterra. At the .05 significance level, the results indicated that the students' learning achievement after learning was significantly higher than before learning. The average level of students' attitudes toward the online game Geography Seterra and e-Learning was the highest (= 4.53, S.D.=0.53), as measured by their opinions on five issues: 1) Playing games facilitates easier memorization of the material; 2) they are entertaining and not monotonous; 3) they can be applied to actual learning; 4) they can be used to study the material before class and review it afterward; and 5) they can be adapted to the requirements of modern study.

Meanwhile, Fantasy Geopolitics encourages students to learn more about their countries by transforming the act of reading the news into a game so that it is no longer perceived as a difficult undertaking (Kim, 2015).

Improved Familiarity with the Location of Countries. This can also be referred to as the locational knowledge the students acquired in the researcher-made geography games. Numerous participants also narrated that their familiarity with the locations of Asian countries was enhanced after the intervention. It can be traced from the concern that students' common difficulty was unfamiliarity with locations. Four participants responded in the post-intervention interview by saying,

After the activities Sir, I gained just like what I have said I gained knowledge from their landmarks, and regions where they are located and I can say that it is good Sir. (IDI 1)

“Mas nadungagan ang mga kahibalo sa mga... asa sila dapita sa Asia Sir. ... naay uban nga nadiscover nako Sir nga kanang kini diay siya na country na dihaa diay siya dapit sa kining sa Asia Sir. Kanang nakatabang siya sa amoa Sir nga maka-gain mi og knowledge about... nadungagan among knowledge sa location nila Sir, sa ilaha nga kanang parts sa Asia.” (IDI 3)

(Our knowledge has increased...about where they are located in Asia Sir. ...there are things I have discovered that this country is located in Asia. It helped us Sir to gain knowledge...about our knowledge of their location, Sir, and on what part they are in Asia.)

“Makabalo kung unsa nga region. After the game Sir, the 6 game Sir, it really helped me before what I’ve said Sir is that kanang difficult kaayu siya I learn pud Sir ba kay kanang naa man guy uban kanang sa ako rapong natun-an sauna Sir kay about sa Philippines ug sa kanang mga simple lang na countries Sir. Unya dili pa kayu anang uban na countries nga layo layo pa kayu Sir. So, kanang karun Sir pag geography games natu Sir kanang maka learn ko more about sa mga countries sa Asia Sir, kung aha siya dapit nga part, unsa ang katapad niya, aha pud siya nga regions Sir.” (IDI 7)

(I know about its region. After the game, the 6 games Sir, it really helped me, like what I’ve said Sir is that it is very difficult for me. I have only learned Sir as to what I have known about the Philippines and other simple countries. Then not those other countries that are not familiar to me, Sir. So, now Sir, when we play the geography games, Sir, I learn more about the countries in Asia to what region a particular country belongs and its neighboring countries Sir.)

“Ma improve ang skills Sir ug mahibal an aha siya nalocate Sir or aha siya na part sa country Sir.” (FGD P6)

(The skills will be improved Sir and it will be known where that country is located or which part of the country Sir.)

Two more participants remarked that their familiarity with the location of Asian countries is enhanced by knowing its outline and shape.

“Kuan Sir maka help kag familiarize Sir nya makahelp pud na sya kuan Sir kung unsay porma ana na country Sir.” (FGD P1)

(It helps us to familiarize Sir, it can also help you Sir, in what shape is that country, Sir.)

“Makabalo ko sa outline niya Sir.” (FGD P7) (I can now outline the countries, Sir.)

Correspondingly, in fact, gaming has a positive effect on the academic performance of students of all ages. The geography game "Geography Prediction" spread on the internet with the slogan "Discover the World" named GeoGuessr, takes its players to many places from Australia's play the game in which one has to determine a location based on five randomly given pictures by using various geographical indicators, players put a mark on the World map and gain points based on the proximity of their mark to the location (Girgin, 2017).

Another study also corroborates to the theme that describes the gained locational knowledge of the students. It is in the study of Davis (2020), where it states that as the 21st century progresses, increasingly sophisticated mapping and gaming techniques will likely become available. Niantic Labs' augmented reality mobile application game Ingress exemplifies the combination of these two topics. At Kutztown University, Ingress has been incorporated to sections of introductory physical geography courses. By providing a unique language-learning platform, mobile gaming can enable students to cultivate and foster geographical inquiries by discovering local locations with cultural, artistic, or arbitrary significance. Through the language of augmented reality gaming, it is hoped that students will learn about the placement of locations, designated as portals in the Ingress architecture, and their significance in the landscape of a community.

Establishes Prior Knowledge of Geography. Students exhibited their understanding of the geography games by completing the sessions. Furthermore, as a result, some participants expressed that it gave them prior knowledge. For instance, IDI 5 expressed that,

“It helps a lot Sir kay for future lessons, maka answer sila. Naa na silay prior knowledge daan kanang sa mga idiscuss sa mga teachers. Kabalo na diay sila ani kanang perfect jud siya sa mga students into geography.”

(It helps a lot Sir because, for future lessons, they can answer. They now have prior knowledge, especially of those topics to be discussed by the teachers. The game is perfect for those students who are into geography.)

Comparably, three other participants have stated that, *“...magamit mana namo Sir as we grow older.” (IDI 2) (...we can use it Sir as we grow older.)*

“... daghang mahibal-an Sir and prior knowledge.” (FGD P7) (...a lot to know Sir and prior knowledge.)

“Maka enhance siya Sir then makatabang jud siya sa amoa Sir kanang labi na sa erm about sa Geographic na mga, for example Sir naa mi discussion Sir, makatabang ang dula Sir kay para kay naa name prior knowledge Sir about sa Geography.” (IDI 3)

(It can enhance us Sir then it can help us, Sir, especially in the erm about the Geographical ones, for example, Sir we have a discussion, Sir, the game will help Sir because we can have prior knowledge Sir about Geography.)

IDI 5 added that it is preferable for students to have prior knowledge of the topics to be discussed. Moreover, if other students lack geographic knowledge, they can teach them.

“Mas maayu man gud nang kanang kuntahay no naay klase tas pangutan-on ta, kabalo nagyud ta daan. Ang uban dili pa tapos pwede nimo sila tudluan.” (IDI 5)

(For example in our classes, it’s better if you know it already. There are others who do not know then you can teach them.)

The interview data demonstrated that students gain confidence because they now possess prior knowledge that can be utilized in future

discussions. They can now have an advantage prior to engaging with the new content.

Positive Influence of Researcher-Made Geography Games on the Learning Behavior of Students

Elicits Interest in Learning Geography. This theme pertains to students inspired and motivated to learn more about geography, specifically naming countries.

It enhances our point of view of countries like Asian countries and other countries. We want to know about or study about this Sir. (IDI 2)

“...tungod atu Sir kay murag na motivate ko Sir na magsearch atu Sir and familiarize.” (FGD P7)

(...because of the game Sir, I seem to be motivated to research Sir, and be familiar.”

In addition, another participant stated that after playing the geography games, she felt compelled to download a geography app and learn more.

“...need pud nako mag research gali ana Sir ug magdulag katung mga imong gipangkuan Sir arun makatuon pagyud Sir.” (FGD P2)
(...I also need to do some research, Sir, and play the games you made us play, Sir so that I can study more.)

Geography provides an excellent opportunity for the development of spatial, naturalistic, and interpersonal intelligences, and providing appropriate feedback to students is a crucial step in enabling them to analyze, interpret, and evaluate their answers. Consideration was given to using gamification techniques to engage and motivate the child (Ramirez et al., 2013)

Similarly, the incorporation of a geography app called Ingress into the geography curriculum may increase students' motivation to learn more about their hometowns, campus communities, and beyond by forging a strong connection between them and the discipline of geography. This emerging learning language has the potential to provide an exciting new direction for the modern education system (Davis, 2020).

In general, the analysis of the performance of students in naming Asian countries after the use of researcher-made geography games is presented through the model below.

Figure 4. *Conclusive Model on the Incorporation of Researcher-Made Geography Games to the Development of Knowledge and Influencing Learning Behavior of Students*

Students' Reflective Insights on the Utilization of Researcher-Made Geography Games as an Intervention to Enhance Students' Performance in Naming Asian Countries That Can Be Shared with Others

As the interview progressed, the researchers asked the students about their experiences and perspectives after playing geography games made by the researchers. Questions in the post-intervention interview include their insights and pieces of advice that they can share with students who also have difficulties in naming Asian countries. Participants' responses can be categorized as having commonalities

because they involve similar concepts during the process. Following the data analysis procedure, the researchers identified four themes.

Table 4. *Themes in Students' Reflective Insights on the Intervention*

Themes	Core Ideas
The Need to Improve Geographical Knowledge	Realized that, as a result of the intervention, we have much to learn about geography, particularly countries. Need to familiarize themselves with many countries, particularly Asia. Must improve our performance in naming Asian countries by learning their capital cities and flags.
Read and Study Geography-Related Materials	Intervention prompts us to study and read materials related to geography. Must read geography books to enhance their performance in identifying Asian countries. Read books, specifically atlases, aided me in becoming acquainted with Asian countries.
Incorporation of Various Approaches in Learning Geography	Use alternative learning strategies when studying geography. To learn more about geography and to aid our performance in naming Asian countries, there are other strategies, to do. Conducting research (browsing), familiarizing, memorization, listening to teachers, asking for assistance, and playing geography apps are additional ways to help.
Fun Learning	Likely to participate and take chances when teachers use engaging and enjoyable learning activities. The aid of the intervention (researcher-made geography games) did not just help us enhance their performance in naming Asian countries but also made their learning fun.

Table 4 displays the main themes that emerged from the participant's responses. This section discusses their insights on the use of the researcher-made geography games as an intervention for enhancing their performance in naming Asian countries, as well as their recommendations for students who struggle with this ability. The main themes are the need to improve geographical knowledge, read and study geography-related materials, incorporation of various approaches in learning geography, and fun learning. The Need to Improve Geographical Knowledge. This theme pertains to students' realizations that, as a result of the intervention, they have much to learn about geography, particularly countries. Four of the participants have narrated,

"I have realized that there are so many countries that I am unfamiliar with Sir and erm I, paningkamotan nako Sir nga mlearn tu nako ang tanan countries Sir." (IDI 1)

(I have realized that there are so many countries that I am unfamiliar with Sir and I will try to learn all the countries, Sir.)

"Maka encounter og mga bag-ong countries, kanang wala pa nako na know Sir ug makabalo ko kung aha dapita or kung unsa ba na sila." (IDI 5)

(I can encounter new countries, which I don't know yet Sir and I will know where they are or what they are like.)

"So after sa geography games Sir, I realized nga daghan pagyud kog dapat mahibal-an sa world gali Sir, about geography. Ug daghan pajud pud kog wala nahibal-an." (FGD P1)

(So after the geography games Sir, I realized that I have to know a lot about the world, Sir, about geography. And there are a lot of things I need to know.)

"Kuan Sir kaning narealize nako nga daghan pa diay kog wala pa nahibal-an nga mga countries Sir. Tapos gamay rapud diay kog nahibal-an atu nga mga country. Tapos siguro kailangan pa nako mag learn pako sa kuan Sir, mag learn pako more Sir para ma improve akong performance." (FGD P6)

(This made me realize that there are many countries that I still don't know about, Sir. Then I know a little bit about these countries. Then maybe I need to learn more from you Sir, learn more Sir to improve my performance.)

A participant have shared that, despite the fact that they have much more to learn, the game has helped them enhance their performance. IDI 1 expressed that,

"During the game Sir, I've realized that there are so many countries that I don't know but with the help of your research Sir, with your activity I gained erm I gained knowledge." (IDI 1)

(During the game Sir, I've realized that there are so many countries that I don't know but with the help of your research Sir, with your activity I gained erm I gained knowledge.)

IDI 3, shares her insight on the sessions that aid their locational knowledge.

"Nga klase klase ilang location Sir then kanang naa jud koy nadiscover nga kanang mga country gali Sir nga dili familiar sa akoo Sir."

Labi natung West Asia. Daghan kog dili familiar na country atu Sir. Mao tu nga nagkasugat among landas na nadiscover nako sila na mga countries.” (IDI 3)

(That there are different locations, Sir, then I discovered that those countries are not familiar to me, Sir. Especially in West Asia. I am not familiar with many countries, Sir. That’s why our paths crossed and I discovered these countries.)

Meanwhile, IDI 5 shares her insight on the session concerning the flags of different countries.

“Na realize nako ang mga difference sa mga flags Sir. Kanang mga neighboring sad Sir, kanang mga tapad na other countries.” (IDI 5)

(I realized the differences in the flags Sir. Those neighboring countries, Sir, those neighbors from other countries.)

Additionally, FGD P6 in the session that discusses capital cities of countries expressed that,

“Nakafamiliarize ko sa mga countries Sir tapos sa iyang mga capital cities ug flag. Need pagyud nako I enhance ako skill, kay naa pagyud lisud I pronounce ug locate.” (FGD P6)

“I was able to familiarize myself with the countries Sir after their capital cities and flags. I really need to enhance my skill, because it’s hard to pronounce and locate.”

Read and Study Geography-Related Materials. Three participants reported that the intervention consequently prompts them to study and read materials related to geography.

“...kanang ano lang gyud Sir, mag pursige lang gyud og kanang study nya mag read og mga books about countries.” (IDI 1)

(...just continue my studies and read books about countries.)

“My advice erm my advice Sir is, also me, myself Sir I have difficulties on naming Asian countries but erm I just erm magpursige lang gyud nga mag study Sir and erm... read books about geography Sir.” (IDI 1)

(My advice erm my advice Sir is, also me, myself Sir I have difficulties on Asian countries but erm I just erm just persevere to study Sir and erm... read books about geography Sir.)

“... mag study, mag read pa Sir.” (IDI 2) (...study, read more Sir.)

“Dili lang man pud atung countries atung dapat I learn naa man pud ang uban countries Sir like kanang do some research and read books.” (IDI 7)

(It’s not just our countries that I should learn there are other countries too Sir like that do some research and read books.)

“Study an atlas Sir. It helped me a lot sa pag name Sir and pag identify sa outline.” (IDI 2)

(Study the atlas Sir. It helped me a lot in naming Sir and identifying the outline.)

Incorporation of Various Approaches in Learning Geography. Based on the responses, it was determined that another insight and advice for students who struggle with naming Asian countries is to utilize alternative learning strategies. Participants’ responses revealed that conducting research (browsing), familiarizing, memorization, listening to teachers, asking for assistance, and playing geography apps are additional ways to help.

“Research about sa mga Asian countries, kanang iprint, kung pwede mamemorize gyud nimo siya Sir. Kay dali raman gyud maka memorize Sir, imong balik-balikon.” (IDI 3)

(Research about Asian countries that you can print, if possible you can really memorize it, Sir. Because it’s really easy to memorize Sir, you just repeat it over and over again.)

“Research lang gyud Sir tas mas maayu man gud ng mag advance study ta kay mas maayu naa kay learning daan labi na kung pangutan- on sa sa imong mga teachers. Research lang gyud and study and try to familiarize kung asa sila dapita.” (IDI 5)

(Just research, sir, but it’s better to do an advanced study because it’s better to learn beforehand, especially if you’re asked by your teachers. Just research and study and try to familiarize yourself with where they are.)

Participants FGD P2, FGD P6, FGD P3, and FGD P7 concurred that listening to teachers, particularly during discussions, is beneficial.

“...maminaw sa discussion sa teacher and kuan Sir kanang try niyang improve iyang skills in memorizing.” (FGD P2)

(...listen to the discussion of the teacher and try to improve their skills in memorizing.)

“...maminaw sila sa maestra Sir.” (FGD P6) (...listen to the teacher Sir.)

“Maminaw sa klase Sir, especially sa Aral Pan” (FGD P3) (Listen in class Sir, especially in Aral. Pan.)

"Paghuman Sir, kung mag tackle og kaning Aral Pan Sir, kay maminaw lang gyud Sir. Kay kung maminaw ka Sir dali raka makatuon Sir." (FGD P7)

(Finally, Sir, if you tackle Aral. Pan. Sir, you really listen, Sir. Because if you listen, Sir, you can learn easily Sir.)

Another participant mentioned that familiarizing ourselves with countries improves performance in naming Asian countries.

"...mag familiarize silag mga country labi ng mga kaning dili kayu ilado ug lisud-lisud pud i pronounce para ang ilang performance Sir is ma improve." (FGD P7)

(...they will familiarize themselves with country especially those that are not well-known and difficult to pronounce so that their performance Sir is improved.)

Another piece of advice shared by IDI 6 stating that

...ask their friends, Sir, maybe they will ask for some help to others that know really well about Asian countries. (IDI 6)

Meanwhile, FGD P1 provided further advice,

"My advice would be Sir kanang download silag game sa ilang phone, about geography." (FGD P1)

(My advice would be Sir that they download a game on their phone, about geography.)

Their insights and recommendations were deemed applicable, as evidenced by the responses indicating that these approaches can improve their ability to name Asian countries.

Fun Learning. Students are more likely to participate and take chances when teachers use engaging and enjoyable learning activities. Students retain information better because the process is enjoyable and memorable when they have fun while learning. Nine out of fourteen responses paralleled the idea presented below.

The geography game is really helpful, it enhances our country-naming because it gives fun to the students while learning and enhancing their ability to name a country Sir. (IDI 6)

"...erm just like what you do to us Sir like kanang magdula'g geography games is important because in order for us students to have a, to gain knowledge Sir and to have a prior knowledge on Asian countries." (IDI 1)

(...erm just like what you do to us Sir like that playing geography games is important because in order for us student to have a, to gain knowledge Sir and to have a prior knowledge on Asian countries.)

"...my insights with the geography games that you, imong gipadula sa amo Sir, helpful Sir and very entertaining." (IDI 2)

(...my insights with the geography games that you, you played with us Sir, helpful Sir and very entertaining.)

"...parehas sa imuha gibuhad Sir...kung dili sila gusto na like boring bitaw ang pag learn nila Sir. Pwede pud mag ano sila, mag dula. Naa manay app ana Sir." (IDI 4)

(...the same as what you did Sir...if they don't want a boring learning for them Sir. They can also play. There is an app for that, Sir.)

"Lingaw kaayu Sir labi na competitive unya mag-away gyud na sila Sir kung unsa gyuy tama na answer. Lingaw siya Sir tapos makatuon sad mi unsaon pag pronounce, unsa iyahang spelling." (IDI 5)

(It's very fun Sir, especially competitive, then they will really fight, Sir, what is the correct answer? It is fun Sir after we learn how to pronounce, how to spell.)

"In my opinion Sir, mas kailangan, it's more important that we use like game Sir for naming the Asian countries like I said it can give fun to the learners while learning Sir." (IDI 6)

(In my opinion Sir, it's needed, it's more important that we use like game Sir for naming the Asian countries like I said it can give fun to the learners while learning Sir.)

"Makaingun pud ko sir na ang game, kay like if our practice teachers or kanang other teachers gud Sir sa kanang historical Sir kay magdula sila ana sa mga bata nga naay difficulties sa pagkabalo sa uban nga country Sir. Para ma master-up pud nila Sir, makabalo gyud nila kung unsa na nga country Sir." (IDI 7)

(I can also say that the game, Sir, if practice teachers or those other teachers, and we will tackle history. They can let students play a game with students who have difficulties in learning from other countries, Sir. In order for them to master up, Sir, they can really know what kind of country it is, Sir.)

"Na realize nako Sir na important pud diay ang geography games Sir kay nadungagan among knowledge about atu Sir then lingaw pud siya nga padula Sir. Mura rakag nag dula dula Sir." (FGD P7)

(I realized, Sir, those geography games are also important, Sir, because we gained additional knowledge about the countries, Sir, also fun to play, Sir. It's like you're playing a game, Sir.)

“Nahappy ko Sir kay nakabalo ko sa mga countries.” (FGD P4) (I'm happy Sir because I already know the countries.)

Correspondingly, gamification has become a popular topic among educators today. Thus, in the study conducted by Erenli (2013), they also developed a game called "QuizeRo" method that is deemed user-friendly. It ought to make teaching more fun.

In addition, although students have a 'big picture' of geography that they prefer not to deviate from, the teacher can influence the depth and detail of students' perceptions by choosing engaging content or activities (Kitchen, 2020). Consequently, based on the responses of the participants, it can be inferred that the games made by the researchers were advantageous for the participants' learning of geography and helped them improve their performance in naming Asian countries. It is corroborated by the study of Mahat et al. (2021), focusing on examining the level of gamification knowledge, gamification skills, and use of gamification among Geography trainee teachers. The study's implications indicate that teachers' gamification strategies must be implemented and aligned with 21st-century learning goals.

In general, the analysis of the students' reflective insights on the utilization of researcher-made geography games as an intervention to enhance students' performance in naming Asian countries that can be shared with others is presented below.

Figure 5. Conclusive Model of Students' Insights on the Intervention that can be Shared with Others

It can be concluded that researcher-made geography games urge students to improve their geography knowledge and enhance their performance in naming Asian countries. The researcher-made geography games also lead them to study, read, and apply alternative learning approaches. Lastly, the researcher-made geography games as an intervention to engage them to learn and have fun naming Asian countries.

Reflection

The study recognizes that students demonstrated poor performance in naming Asian countries by expressing the difficulties such as being unfamiliar with Asian countries, ineptness with their location, and struggles in the correct pronunciation and spelling of country names. All leads to one factor they only have average knowledge and performance in naming Asian countries. For this reason, the teacher-researchers acknowledge the importance of teaching approaches or strategies being utilized to achieve the goal of the new curriculum in prioritizing the development of Filipino students' attitudes towards learning, academic performances, and the acquisition of 21st-century learning skills.

Throughout the implementation of the intervention, the researchers have encountered obstacles. A significant challenge is the implementation of the intervention in the classroom. Since they are allocated as pre-teachers at a cooperating school where the School Principal recommends avoiding class interruptions during class time, it should be used exclusively for instruction and class discussion. Despite the time and schedule constraints, the researchers' strategy maximizes time spent achieving the intervention's objectives. This is accomplished by ensuring effective classroom and time management.

Aside from that, the participation of the students is another challenge. Establishing expectations that students will participate, providing students with a clear idea of what to expect regarding participation, and assigning a grade for students' performance in discussion and the intervention all increase student participation during intervention administration.

Despite the challenges encountered, the researchers' intervention was a complete success, particularly in enhancing the observed difficulty of students' performance by implementing the researchers-made intervention.

Game-based integration in education can be identified as a learning aid for students. Numerous institutions now incorporate game design elements into educational settings. This maximizes learners' enjoyment and engagement by captivating their interest and sustaining their motivation to continue learning. The use of researcher-made geography games as a strategy to enhance students' performance to name Asian countries is consequently consistent with the concept of integrating games into learning.

Lastly, the study's results prove that the intervention significantly influences students' performance through the gained knowledge and their learning behavior, yet still makes learning enjoyable.

Action Plan

In determining whether the intervention – researcher-made geography games – is an effective method for enhancing students' performance to name Asian countries, it needs an action plan. The researchers meticulously planned their processes and actions before the pre-implementation, implementation, and post-implementation phases. Consequently, the researchers present the study's action plan, which includes the objectives, activities/strategies, responsible parties, resources/tools, success indicator, and timeframe, and demonstrates the comprehensive research procedure:

During the pre-implementation stage, classroom observation was conducted to document observed learning issues. Then, the appropriate intervention to resolve the problem is conceptualized. Before the implementation phase, the researchers submitted their research proposal to the technical review committee for evaluation and approval after obtaining approval from the DDOSC-Research Ethics Committee. Then, the pre-intervention assessment is conducted.

In the implementation phase, students will be administered the intervention and introduced to the activities created by the researchers, along with the associated directions. Student participation is also added in this phase to increase engagement in the intervention. Another is the time/schedule of the intervention which added to maximize the allotted time given. On the other hand, post-implementation assessment follows the same procedures as pre-intervention assessment. Observation and evaluation are followed by reflection. Then, the research manuscript is finalized for technical review.

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